

**THE UNIVERSITY
OF QUEENSLAND**
A U S T R A L I A

Insect Classifier for FarmBot

by

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Prof Michael Brünig,

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Dear Professor Brünig,

In accordance with the requirements of the Degree of Bachelor of Engineering (Honours) in the School of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science, I submit the following thesis entitled

“Insect Classifier for FarmBot”

The thesis was performed under the supervision of Matthew D’Souza. I declare that the work submitted in the thesis is my own, except as acknowledged in the text and footnotes, and that it has not previously been submitted for a degree at the University of Queensland or any other institution.

Yours sincerely

James Chen-Smith

To ...

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Abstract

Insect pests have long been a problem for agricultural production, with chemicals and natural enemies historically used for control. However, climate change has exacerbated the challenge of pest management, causing 40% of the world's crops to be lost to pests annually. Effective and sustainable methods for insect pest management are critical, and the proposed project aims to address a gap in knowledge by designing an interoperable acoustic classifier subsystem for FarmBot-based crop management systems. The subsystem will utilize acoustic sensor, a Raspberry Pi 3B and a Jetson Nano System on Chip for insect detection and classification. The project will involve developing a pre-processing pipeline and training a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) using insect sounds. The goal is to create a prototype that accurately classifies insect sounds, which will ultimately lead to higher crop yields, reduced pesticide use, and increased food security.

Contents

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS.....	4
ABSTRACT.....	5
1 INTRODUCTION.....	8
1.1 AIMS.....	9
2 TECHNICAL BACKGROUND.....	10
2.1 MACHINE LEARNING.....	10
2.1.1 <i>Supervised and Unsupervised Learning</i>	10
2.1.2 <i>Classification and Regression</i>	11
2.1.3 <i>K-Nearest Neighbors</i>	11
2.1.4 <i>Multi-Layer Perceptron</i>	11
2.1.5 <i>Convolutional Neural Networks</i>	12
2.2 PRE-PROCESSING.....	13
2.2.1 <i>Pre-emphasis Filtering</i>	13
2.2.2 <i>Signal Segmentation/Framing</i>	13
2.2.3 <i>Fourier Transform (Spectrograms)</i>	14
2.2.4 <i>Mel-Frequency</i>	15
2.2.5 <i>Mel-Spectrogram</i>	15
2.2.6 <i>MFCCs and DCT</i>	16
2.2.7 <i>LFCCs</i>	17
2.2.8 <i>Feature Images</i>	17
2.3 HARDWARE BACKGROUND.....	18
2.3.1 <i>FarmBot Genesis</i>	18
2.3.2 <i>Raspberry Pi 3</i>	19
2.3.3 <i>Nvidia Jetson Nano</i>	19
3 LITERATURE REVIEW.....	21
3.1 PILOT STUDIES.....	21
3.2 PILOT STUDIES (SUMMARY).....	23
3.4 DATASETS FOR CLASSIFICATION TRAINING.....	25
3.5 FARMBOT ACOUSTIC ARRAY CLASSIFIER.....	25
3.6 FARMBOT CROP IMAGE CLASSIFIER.....	25
3.7 KNOWLEDGE GAP.....	26
4 METHODOLOGY.....	27

4.1	DATASET	27
4.1.1	<i>Pre-processing</i>	28
4.1.2	<i>Batch Preprocessing</i>	30
4.1.3	<i>Dataset Balancing</i>	31
4.2	MODEL SELECTION.....	32
4.2.1	<i>Stopping Condition</i>	32
4.2.2	<i>K-Fold Cross Validation</i>	33
4.2.3	<i>Hyperparameter Optimization (Grid Search)</i>	34
4.3	HARDWARE DEPLOYMENT	35
4.4	BACKEND STACK.....	36
4.4.1	<i>Configuration File</i>	36
4.4.2	<i>Real-Time Classification Pipeline</i>	36
4.4.3	<i>Web Stack</i>	37
4.4.4	<i>Data API</i>	38
4.5	FRONTEND DESIGN	40
4.6	SUMMARY.....	43
5	RESULTS.....	44
5.1	CLASSIFICATION MODEL	44
5.2	REAL-TIME CLASSIFICATION PIPELINE.....	47
5.3	FRONTEND	48
6	CONCLUSION	50
6.1	FUTURE DIRECTIONS	51
7	FIGURES	52
8	REFERENCES	54
9	APPENDICES.....	57
9.1	APPENDIX A: GRID SEARCH RESULTS	57

1 Introduction

Insect pests have been a persistent threat to human agricultural production since time immemorial, competing with humans for crop yields. Throughout history, chemical agents including sulfur and various herbal compounds have been used to control insect pests that damage crops [2] while many natural enemies have been introduced, some of which – including cane toads – have caused disproportionate harm to the environment [3]. Moreover, in recent years, climate change has exacerbated the challenge of pest management, as it is estimated that 40% of the world's crops are lost to pests each year [4]. Climate change can also alter the behaviors of insect pests in a variety of ways, including but not limited to distribution, appearance, and interaction with species of animals and crops [5].

The digital age has granted humans a variety of novel approaches to prevent and minimize the damage caused by insect pests, including the development of systems aimed at monitoring their presence, abundance, and variety in key agricultural environments. These automated systems, which comprise of a set of distributed sensors, continuously monitor insect activity in some crop adjacent area. These systems integrate with automated and manually implemented external peripherals such as light traps, pan traps, bucket traps and sticky paper traps to subdue problematic insect activity. In addition to integration with peripherals, insect monitoring systems can also provide real-time information needed to select optimal mitigation strategies.

Integrated Pest Management (IPM) systems are a type of insect monitoring system that reduces the need for pesticides and offer an environmentally friendly, sustainable alternative for handling insects in agricultural production [6]. Insect monitoring systems can also help agricultural personnel save time, resources, and labor, which would otherwise be spent on crop maintenance.

Past projects have primarily been centered around the classification of insects in two steps: 1) To transform (pre-process) the data into some frequency space (spectrogram) via techniques such as Fourier Transform and 2) To train and classify spectrogram images using deep learning techniques with generic or custom networks involving convolution.

Though past projects have shed light on the deep learning and pre-processing front, there has not been a single project where this has applied to integration with the FarmBot platform.

Furthermore, there are currently very few projects which integrate the Nvidia Jetson Nano with the FarmBot platform.

The plan of this project is to develop a deep learning classifier model which classifies insect sounds in a database to a reasonable degree. And then to modify and/or append the dataset with additional data as required. And finally, to integrate the classification system with a FarmBot based system.

This report details a preliminary design for a weather resistant Acoustic Sensor Array Classifier that can identify insects based on their acoustic signature. The classifier is to be integrated into pre-existing FarmBot environments, taking advantage of a Nvidia Jetson Nano System on Chip (SoC).

1.1 Aims

The aim of this project is to design and implement an interoperable acoustic classifier subsystem for FarmBot-based crop management systems. The subsystem will utilize microphone(s), placeable on some plant bed, to provide acoustic input for insect detection. The Jetson Nano System on Chip (SoC) will be used to process the data streams and pre-process audio recordings. A Raspberry Pi will use suitable empirical models such as machine learning to classify the insects. The proposed acoustic classifier module should integrate seamlessly with the FarmBot system, operate autonomously, be capable of classifying/quantifying insect activity in real-time and provide end-users with the ability to view this information through a somewhat intuitive graphical interface.

2 Technical Background

To gain a deeper understanding of the challenges involved in empirically classifying insects using acoustic data, including machine learning and visualization, a comprehensive review of the relevant literature and topic-adjacent past projects was conducted. A review of the related hardware platforms and peripherals was also conducted.

To identify the most effective machine learning model for the acoustic classification of insects, topic-adjacent models and architectures, and their associated feasibility for this specific project will be evaluated. The background and capabilities of the FarmBot platform will also be explored, which will provide useful support for this project.

2.1 Machine Learning

Machine learning is an applied field of Artificial Intelligence (AI) that has been popular for at least 25 years [7]. It allows models to be trained based on patterns in empirical observations of sets of data, without requiring formally derived models for mapping relationships between variables. These models can then be used to make generalized inferences (predictions) based on new inputs given. These inferences can also be used to reveal trends within the data that help improve decision making and optimize the efficiency of target systems [8].

2.1.1 Supervised and Unsupervised Learning

Several forms of machine learning methods exist, including supervised learning, unsupervised learning and reinforcement learning, each with its own advantages [8].

Supervised learning is a method involving heuristic or manually labelled data, which maps from each item in the dataset to its associated truth value. Common supervised methods involve the use of a Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Bayes classifiers which makes use of higher-dimensional spaces to better separate the dataset between two (or more) classes [9].

Unsupervised learning – also known as reinforcement learning, in contrast, is a method of machine learning that does not require labelled input data, but rather learns through representation, which attempts to derive hidden structure in the data. It assumes that physical objects and events tend to have limited complexity and can be described in a small number of

bits. A general principle of unsupervised learning is to minimize entropy, that is, to derive some representation such that redundancy contained in the input data is minimized. Another principle is sparse coding, which aims to minimize the number of units in a distributed network that are activated by the input data – this often involves placing a limit on the number of neurons that are allowed to be active at any given time by way of a hyperparameter [10].

2.1.2 Classification and Regression

Machine learning problems can generally be described in terms of 2 types, classification, and regression problems.

Classification problems involve prediction, which is a process that involves finding a function that will accurately map to some discrete variable y given some input variable x . Regression problems, in contrast, involve mapping to some continuous value of y given a continuous input x [11].

2.1.3 K-Nearest Neighbors

The K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) algorithm is a relatively easy to implement algorithm which consists of taking a subset of k -datapoints, and for classification – i.e., the scope of this project – takes a majority vote of which class appears most frequently in this subset. There are multiple distance metrics available for KNN, of which Euclidean distance is a popular one [12].

The Euclidean distance between target point p_1 and surrounding point p_2 in n dimensions can be generalized as:

$$d(p_1, p_2) = \sqrt{\sum_{n=1}^N (p_{1n} - p_{2n})^2}$$

2.1.4 Multi-Layer Perceptron

The Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) is a type of neural network capable of classifying datasets which are non-linearly separable. It works by incorporating non-linear activation functions (i.e., neurons) and weight/bias inputs, into a series of fully connected layers to determine some point

on the gradient of the feature plane. Backpropagation is performed on the corresponding activation function at the output layer to minimize some loss function [13].

Figure 2.1.a Multi-Layer Perceptron Network [13]

The outputs of the output layer are typically logits (i.e. SoftMax activation function), that is, it is a layer which produces probabilities of the input being each class in some multi-class classification problem [14].

2.1.5 Convolutional Neural Networks

A Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is a deep learning algorithm which can be used to classify images. In extremely basic binary images, an MLP may suffice, but when it comes to complex images with pixel dependencies, CNNs vastly outperform MLPs. A CNN is capable of capturing all the spatial neighborhoods within pixel neighborhoods of an image and hence understand the sophistication of images better [15].

Figure 2.1.b Convolutional Neural Network Diagram [15]

2.2 Pre-processing

Preprocessing is a crucial part of acoustic classification, as it is required to transform acoustic signals into a format suitable for machine learning.

2.2.1 Pre-emphasis Filtering

Pre-emphasis is a signal processing technique primarily aimed at increasing the quality and intelligibility of time-varying acoustic signals, it achieves this through increasing energy at higher frequencies [16]. This is accomplished as high-frequency components of signals tend to have larger changes in amplitude between frames. The formula for pre-emphasis is shown below:

$$y[n] = x[n] - \alpha x[n - 1]$$

Where:

- $y[n]$ is the output for frame n .
- $x[n]$ is the input for frame n .
- α is a coefficient usually $\alpha \in [0.9, 1]$

2.2.2 Signal Segmentation/Framing

Segmentation is the process of partitioning the signal into a set of signals of equal length. The frame length must be chosen to include all the segments considered [16]. The formula for signal segmentation/framing is shown below:

$$y[n, m] = x[ns_{hop} + m]$$

Where:

- $y[n, m]$ is the value of the m^{th} sample in the n^{th} frame $n \in [0, N), m \in [0, s_{frame})$
where:
 - N is the total amount of frames that fit within the length of the input signal.
 - s_{frame} is the frame size, calculated by using $s_{frame} = 2 \times \text{round}(\frac{t_{frame} \times sr}{2})$,
where:

- $round()$ denotes a function which rounds some float to the nearest integer.
 - t_{frame} is the frame duration in seconds.
 - sr is the sampling rate in Hz .
- x is the input signal values.
- s_{hop} is the hop size, calculated by using $s_{hop} = round(t_{step} \times sr)$, where:
 - $round()$ denotes a function which rounds some float to the nearest integer.
 - t_{step} is the time step of each hop in seconds.
 - sr is the sampling rate in Hz .

2.2.3 Fourier Transform (Spectrograms)

A spectrogram (Figure 2.2.a) is a visual representation of an acoustic signal, it plots time on the x-axis and frequency on the y-axis. Different colors are used to indicate varying amplitudes with respect to frequency and time [17].

Figure 2.2.a Spectrogram [17]

Spectrograms are produced using Fourier Transforms to decompose signals into their constituent frequencies. In general, the Discrete Fourier transform function can be written as follows:

$$X[k] = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} x[n] e^{-j\frac{2\pi}{N}nk}$$

Where:

- $X[k]$ is the complex amplitude of the signal in the frequency domain at frequency f , $x(k)$ is the time-domain signal to be transformed.

2.2.4 Mel-Frequency

Since the spectrogram generated by a simple Fourier Transform does not accurately reflect human hearing perception, many papers have taken advantage of the Mel-Frequency scale – a more accurate representation of human acoustic perception [16]. The formula for computing the Mel-frequency based on standard frequency is shown below:

$$M(f) = 2595 \log_{10} \left(1 + \left(\frac{f}{700} \right) \right)$$

When compared to standard spectrograms which plot frequency against time, the Mel spectrogram [18]:

- Uses the Mel scale instead of the frequency on the $m(t)$ – Mel w.r.t. time – axis.
- Uses the decibel ($dB = 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{V_{amplitude}}{V_{reference}} \right)$) scale instead of absolute amplitude.

The spectrogram is like the regular spectrogram, where the Mel frequency is represented on y-axis, with respect to time, while the decibel amplitude is represented as a value for some $dB(t, m(t))$ pair [18].

Figure 2.2.b Mel Spectrogram [18]

2.2.5 Mel-Spectrogram

For the Mel-Spectrum Cepstrum Coefficients (MFCCs) to be calculated, the Mel filter bank must be applied to the linear (or a power) spectrogram to produce the Mel spectrogram. The Mel filter banks can be described using triangle filters, which are narrower at low frequencies and wider at

high frequencies (Figure 2.2.c). The first frequency of each filter bank is calculated using the inverse formula of the Mel scale at that frequency [16].

Figure 2.2.c Mel Filter Banks [16]

The center frequencies of each filter bank frequency can be calculated with the following equation:

$$m_i = M(f_{lower}) + \frac{(n - 1) (M(f_{upper}) - M(f_{lower}))}{(N - 1)}$$

Where:

- m_i is the center frequency at filter bank bandwidth $n \in [1, n_{filters}]$, $N \in \mathbb{N}$.
- f_{upper} and f_{lower} are upper and lower bounds for that bandwidth range.

To calculate the Mel spectrogram S_{Mel} , a dot product is performed between the Mel filter bank F_{Mel} and the linear spectrogram S_{Lin} for each time varying vector in the spectrogram:

$$S_{Mel} = F_{Mel} \cdot S_{Lin}$$

2.2.6 MFCCs and DCT

Discrete Cosine Transformation (DCT) is performed on the log Mel spectrogram to obtain Mel-Frequency Cepstrum Coefficients (MFCCs) [19, 20]. To calculate the log Mel spectrogram $S_{\log(Mel)}$, the log of every time varying vector of the Mel spectrogram S_{Mel} is taken:

$$S_{\log(Mel)} = \log(\max(S_{Mel}, \alpha))$$

Where:

- α is a small value, i.e. 10^{-10} , to prevent taking logarithms of values ≤ 0 .

Finally, the log Mel spectrogram is processed into MFCCs by taking the DCT[16]:

$$c_n = \sum_{k=1}^{n_{filters}} \ln(x_k) \cos\left(\frac{\pi(k-0.5)n}{n_{filters}}\right), \quad \forall n \in [1, n_{cepstrums}]$$

Where:

- c_n represents cepstrum n in the MFCC.
- x_k is the $k \in [1, n_{filters}]$ filtered component of the log Mel spectrogram.

These MFCCs can then be classified using Support Vector Machines (SVM), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNNs), Random Forests and Deep Learning methodologies.

2.2.7 LFCCs

LFCCs (Linear Frequency Cepstral Coefficients) are like MFCCs, except they are generated using a linear scaled filter bank instead, which uses equidistantly spaced triangle filters with the same width as opposed to a Mel-scaled filter bank.

2.2.8 Feature Images

Once acoustic signals have been transformed into frequency-time domain, either with a linear spectrogram, Mel spectrogram or MFCCs, it can be input into a deep learning architecture – such as standard CNNs – to process them and extract feature maps, which represent the encoded spectrogram image. Once the feature maps have been generated, they can be used to classify new inputs using a set of fully connected layers [17].

2.3 Hardware Background

2.3.1 FarmBot Genesis

FarmBot is an open-source integrated Computer Numerical Control (CNC) based crop management system which individually manages crops, by seeding, watering and removing weeds from small garden beds. Once built, FarmBot systems performs “nearly the entire gardening process prior to harvesting [21].

The primary model of FarmBot is the FarmBot Genesis, which is comprised of a specialized garden bed of up-to $18m^3$, a 3-axis tool mount – actuated by 4 NEMA 17 stepper motors, capable of moving the tool to any point on the garden bed [22].

Figure 2.3.a FarmBot Genesis Garden Mechanism [22]

The Genesis is controlled by an embedded CNC “Farmduino” board (Figure 2.3.b) which is connected to the motors, as well as other peripherals situated on the tool mount, including a vacuum pump, water solenoid valve, LED light-strip, power and data to the Raspberry Pi as well as spare peripheral ports [22].

Figure 2.3.b Farmduino I/O Overview [22]

2.3.2 Raspberry Pi 3

The Raspberry Pi 3 is an ARM based Single Board Computer (SBC) like the Jetson Nano.

2.3.3 Nvidia Jetson Nano

The Jetson Nano Developer Kit (Figure 2.4.d) was released by NVIDIA as a high-performance machine-learning optimized ARM single board computer (SBC). The Nano – with its ARM® Cortex®-A57 processor and 128-core NVIDIA Maxwell™ GPU – allows for a computation performance of up to 472 billion floating point operations per second. The Nano has 4GB of 64-bit LPDDR4 memory and contains an onboard microSD card slot for expandable storage [23].

While the performance of the Jetson Nano’s CPU is inferior to that of the Raspberry Pi 4’s Cortex-A72 CPU, it is superior to that of the Raspberry Pi 3’s Cortex-A57. Furthermore, the Jetson Nano, has far superior parallel computational capabilities with its CUDA compatible GPU [24].

When it comes to software, the Jetson Nano allows for a variety of ARM compatible Linux distributions to be installed. The recommended operating system is a version of Ubuntu desktop with the JetPack SDK and NVIDIA CUDA Toolkit preinstalled. This operating system enables interface with programming languages such as Python and machine learning libraries such as PyTorch, cuDNN, and Tensorflow Keras [23]. This allows for a multitude of deep learning network architectures to be trained with varying performances (Figure 2.3.c).

As of writing, the Jetson Nano has a per-unit cost of \$165AUD on Amazon [25].

Figure 2.3.c Jetson Nano FPS Performance w.r.t DL Network [23]

- 1) microSD card slot for main storage
- 2) 40-pin expansion header
- 3) Micro-USB port for 5V power input, or for Device Mode
- 4) Gigabit Ethernet port
- 5) USB 3.0 ports (x4)
- 6) HDMI output port
- 7) DisplayPort connector
- 8) DC Barrel jack for 5V power input
- 9) MIPI CSI-2 camera connectors [1]

Figure 2.3.d Jetson Nano Overview [1]

3 Literature Review

3.1 Pilot Studies

The literature review reveals a progression in the methods used for spectrum image classification and insect sound recognition, showing an increasing reliance on deep learning techniques for higher accuracy. Initial approaches transformed audio signals into Fourier space via Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) before applying machine learning classifiers. A study utilizing FFT with AlexNet, a deep convolutional neural network (CNN), and a Support Vector Machine (SVM) for classification, exceeded the accuracy of systems that used FFT with SVM alone [26].

Exploration of enhanced spectrograms using Contrast-Limit Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE) coupled with CNNs indicated significant improvements in classification accuracy over traditional spectrograms and common feature extraction techniques like Mel-Frequency Cepstrum Coefficients (MFCCs). Notably, a study applying CLAHE to the USDA “Bug Bytes” dataset demonstrated superior performance with a CNN, achieving an accuracy of 0.9787 [27].

In the context of processing variable-length audio signals, end-to-end classification methods using 1-dimensional CNNs have been employed. This involves splitting the audio into fixed-length frames with a carefully chosen sliding window to handle environmental sounds of various durations effectively [28].

Data augmentation techniques, including time shift, stretch, and data mix-up, were shown to significantly improve prediction accuracies. Additionally, Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), such as Deep Convolutional GANs (DCGANs), were employed for augmenting data by generating varied samples in [29, 30].

The adoption of Residual Networks (ResNets), particularly the Wide ResNet model, has been tailored for acoustic signals, striking a balance between training efficiency and classification accuracy [20]. Moreover, the novel ACDNet architecture was introduced, outperforming previous models and designed to operate on resource-constrained devices. ACDNet focuses on convolutional layers and features extraction blocks tailored for spectral and temporal features, achieving high classification accuracy with a relatively low computational demand [31].

A meta-analysis conducted by the United States Department of Agriculture reviewed methods for detecting insects in stored grain, discussing various preprocessing and classification techniques without specifying an implementation. This indicates a potential gap for further research in functional systems tailored to the acoustic identification of insects in different environmental conditions [32].

Lastly, historical accuracies of insect sound classification methods, as tabulated, show a trend toward increased accuracy from 2017 to 2018, moving from linear SVMs and MFCCs to CNN-based methods, aligning with the advancements discussed [16, 27].

The following table lists the insect classification accuracies in past papers:

Pipeline	Dataset	Accuracy	Year	Source
Low-Level Feature Set + Linear SVM	Bug Bytes sound library: stored product insect pest sounds	0.822	2017	[16]
MFCC + Linear SVM	Bug Bytes sound library: stored product insect pest sounds	0.887	2017	[16]
MFCC + CNN	Bug Bytes sound library: stored product insect pest sounds	0.936	2018	[27]
CLAHE + CNN	Bug Bytes sound library: stored product insect pest sounds	0.978	2018	[27]

3.2 Pilot Studies (Summary)

Below is a list of the past studies related to the classification of insects based on acoustic signals:

Author(s)	Title	Year	Source	Peer Reviewed
Zhang C, et al.	Turning wingbeat sounds into spectrum images for acoustic insect classification	2014	[26]	Yes
Phung Q, et al.	Automated Insect Detection Using Acoustic Features Based on Sound Generated from Insect Activities	2017	[16]	Yes
Dong X, et al.	Insect Sound Recognition Based on Convolutional Neural Network	2018	[27]	Yes
Noda J, et al.	Acoustic Classification of Singing Insects Based on MFCC/LFCC Fusion	2019	[19]	Yes
Abdoli S, et al.	End-to-end environmental sound classification using a 1D convolutional neural network	2019	[28]	Yes
Nugroho A, et al.	Development of cloud-based bioacoustics monitoring system for supporting Integrated Pest Management in agriculture production	2020	[33]	Yes
Hibino S, et al.	Classification of singing insect sounds with convolutional neural network	2021	[29]	Yes
Mankin R, et al.	Automated Applications of Acoustics for Stored Product Insect Detection, Monitoring, and Management	2021	[32]	Yes
Effendy N, et al.	Forest quality assessment based on bird sound recognition using convolutional neural networks	2022	[20]	Yes
Höchst J, et al.	Bird@Edge: Bird Species Recognition at the Edge	2022	[34]	Yes
Bahmei Behnaz, et al.	CNN-RNN and Data Augmentation Using Deep Convolutional Generative	2022	[30]	Yes

	Adversarial Network for Environmental Sound Classification			
Mohaimenuzzaman B, et al.	Environmental Sound Classification on the Edge: A Pipeline for Deep Acoustic Networks on Extremely Resource-Constrained Devices	2023	[31]	Yes
Rustia D, et al.	Intelligent Insect Monitoring Systems	2023	[6]	No

3.4 Datasets for Classification Training

The following table lists all the datasets mentioned in past papers:

Author(s)	Title	Description	Year	Source
Mankin R	Bug Bytes sound library: stored product insect pest sounds	The dataset includes 47 types of insect sounds, with each containing 1-10 recordings [27].	2020	[35]
Various Authors	Google AudioSet	AudioSet consists of an expanding ontology of 632 audio event classes and a collection of 2,084,320 human-labeled 10-second sound clips drawn from YouTube videos.		[36]

3.5 Farmbot Acoustic Array Classifier

A similar project was completed in 2021 at the University of Queensland, by Tunyun He, which included an insect classification system based on a similar MFCC based pre-processor and a KNN/SVM based classification model. The thesis demonstrated a proof-of-concept for insect classification systems involving the Jetson Nano, Raspberry Pi and MATRIX Voice platforms, achieving a peak accuracy of approximately 93.4% on an unknown dataset [37].

Attempts to contact the author in regard to project specifics (i.e. datasets) have been unsuccessful.

3.6 Farmbot Crop Image Classifier

A similar project was completed in 2020 at the University of Queensland, by Jiajun Tian, which involved creating a subsystem for FarmBot based systems, designed to identify and categorize the lifecycle of plants. The project involves the same Jetson Nano SBC as in this proposed project.

Finally, the report outlines some potential changes which could've improved the performance of the model:

- Expansion of the dataset, which was limited by the available space on the FarmBot.
- Enhancement of computational performances and issues related to memory overflow.

3.7 Knowledge Gap

Though there exists a multitude of past papers documenting the development and implementation of plant crop classification systems designed on the FarmBot platform, there exists a gap in knowledge when it comes to the classification of insect pests. And though there is a multitude of research on the application and theory of IPMs involving acoustic classification, there are no current papers which outline how these systems can be integrated with FarmBot based crop management systems.

There are essentially no published studies in the past which detail the integration of FarmBot systems with Jetson Nano based SBCs. If conducted, this project will be one of the few. Most past research are centered around traditional pattern recognition algorithms, which provide a decent degree of prediction accuracy, but are however complex and time-consuming to “handcraft” and implement. The purpose of this project is to implement some “generic” model which provides the best results, whilst maintaining simplicity.

4 Methodology

Please note for the following sections:

- A *sample* refers to an audio file or feature image belonging to the training/valuation set.
- A *recording* refers to an audio file collected as a part of the test set.
- A *signal* refers to either a *sample* or a *recording*.
- A *segment* refers to a segmented subset of an audio file.

4.1 Dataset

In the process of collecting insect sounds, a few considerations were made. Firstly, it was assumed that the manual collection (of insect sounds) will be outside the scope of this project. Therefore, it was decided that they were to be collected, in part, from online datasets. Secondly, due to the poor documentation of datasets in the existing literature, results in this project will not be consistent with those studies.

The insect sound data in this project were derived from mainly 4 sources, Mankin's *Bug Bytes* dataset, Google AudioSet, YouTube and manual samplings. The scope of the insect categories was limited to Crickets and Flies as the features of the two classes have been previously studied and serves as a benchmark for this project[37].

The *Bug Bytes* dataset was obtained as a single .zip format, whereas AudioSet was obtained via a Python script to download labelled clips from YouTube and trim based on a spreadsheet of labelled segments.

```
subset_ids = {
    "Fly": "/m/0h2mp",
    "Cricket": "/m/09xqv",
}

audioset = AudioSet(subset_ids)
audioset_train, audioset_test = audioset.get_rows_relevant()
audioset.download_relevant(audioset_test, audioset.path_output_test)
```

4.1.1 Pre-processing

For an audio signal to be processed by a convolutional neural network, it must be converted to suitable feature format, i.e., spectral images. In this project, MFCCs/LFCCs were the chosen feature extraction method, since MFCCs/LFCCs have been shown to provide higher accuracies and lower space complexities when compared to raw spectrograms [16]. The Librosa and TorchAudio libraries were used for audio segmentation and feature extraction.

A band-pass filter was not implemented since the preprocessor was designed to allow for greater generalization as some insect species may fall outside of the frequency range for flies and crickets. Additionally, CNNs (as used in this project) are more robust to noise compared to models such as k-NNs, hence the impact of data cleanup may not be as important.

Figure 4.1.a Librosa Pre-processor Block Diagram

A set of operations (Figure 4.1.a) was performed to transform the input signal into MFCC/LFCC spectral images using the Librosa library, however this was later replaced with the TorchAudio library to optimize performance and minimize overhead.

The following parameters were used for the Preprocessor class in this project:

- For pre-emphasis, TorchVision’s default coefficient value of 0.97 was used.
- For generating the MFCC and LFCC images, the number of triangle filters that were used was 26. This is in line with the filter bank size in past projects involving insect classification and was set to better replicate past results. *The development of a “state-of-the-art” preprocessor is outside the scope of this project.*
- The MFCC size was set to 13.
- The LFCC size was set to 13.

Figure 4.1.b TorchAudio Preprocessor Diagram [38]

The process of creating the MFCC (Figure 4.1.b) involves firstly a conversion of the input signal into frequency space (power spectrogram) via a fourier transform, followed by applying the Mel-scaled filter bank and performing DCT to create the MFCCs, or simply taking the DCT to create the LFCCs.

Figure 4.1.c Sample [MFCC, LFCC] Feature Image for Cricket

The final feature image (Figure 4.1.c) is a vertical ($26 \times n$) concatenation of the MFCC and LFCC images, where the upper 13 pixels correspond to the 13 MFCCs and lower 13 pixels represent the LFCCs. The time dimension moves along in the horizontal direction.

This technique was chosen since the concatenation of MFCCs with LFCCs has been shown to enhance classification performance in the literature [19, 37]

4.1.2 Batch Preprocessing

After the pre-processor was implemented, a Generator class was implemented to automate the pre-processing pipeline. It implements the Preprocessor class and allows for entire folders of raw samples to be processed into MFCC/LFCC spectral images at once.

Figure 4.1.d Dataset Folder Structure

The entire training/validation set is contained within the *dataset* folder, the raw audio samples are in the folders under *dataset* (Figure 4.1.d). The *generated* subfolder contains the MFCC/LFCC samples generated by the preprocessor.

The Generator class performs the following operations:

1. The audio sample is loaded and converted into mono and resampled to 16,000Hz. This value was chosen as it was found to be a good tradeoff between input resolution and computational cost in the literature [28].
2. MFCC and LFCC images are generated for each complete segment of the signal (the last partial segment is discarded).
3. MFCC and LFCC images are concatenated into a single image sample.
4. The image samples are normalized as 8-bit unsigned integers and are saved as .png files in the output folder under *generated* corresponding to the folder name in *dataset*.

The system was designed to ensure generalizability as more classes may be added simply by creating more folders and adding audio samples into each and re-generating the image samples.

4.1.3 Dataset Balancing

After implementing a proof-of-concept MLP model to test the pre-processed feature images, it was observed that the output probabilities consistently favored classes with the most samples. This class imbalance led to skewed classification results, undermining the model's predictive accuracy for minority classes.

Figure 4.1.e Undersampling and Oversampling [39]

To address this issue, two common techniques were considered: oversampling the minority classes and undersampling the majority classes (Figure 4.1.e). Oversampling involves artificially inflating the size of minority classes by adding copies or generating new instances, which could risk overfitting. Undersampling, on the other hand, reduces the size of the majority class by randomly eliminating instances until all classes have the same number of samples [40].

Figure 4.1.f Dataset Size Before/After Resampling

After evaluating the benefits of each method, the decision was made to proceed with undersampling. Random deletion was applied to the datasets to equalize the number of samples across classes (Figure 4.1.f).

4.2 Model Selection

In this project, a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) was selected as the Machine Learning model. This decision was made since most “state of the art” models utilize CNNs or some combination of CNNs with some other custom network.

The decision was made to use a basic CNN with 2 convolutional layers and 1 fully-connected layers since this configuration was shown to be effective [27]. Additionally, there are challenges associated with custom models including:

- Difficulty to document and be understood by third-party developers.
- May be too large to run on low-powered SBCs.
- May be more time consuming to train for any increased accuracy it may provide.

4.2.1 Stopping Condition

To systematically evaluate the model and to provide consistent results, a few approaches to stopping (breaking out of the) training loop were considered including:

n-Epochs

This was the most straightforward stopping strategy. The n-Epochs approach stops the training loop when n epochs have been completed. However, this approach is disadvantaged in that various models could require various number of epochs to complete, and this number can even vary between multiple training runs for the same model.

Moving Accuracy

The moving accuracy strategy systematically stops the model when the last n accuracies exceed a set percentage. This approach is superior to the n-Epochs approach as it can adapt to models of varying complexities and behaviors. However, this approach is prone to overfitting, as the model may converge without the moving average threshold being met.

Best For (Patience)

The “best for” strategy stops the model if an epoch accuracy has been reached, such that the accuracy has been the best for the last n epochs. This provides a systematic method to stop the training loop.

All three strategies were implemented for this project, however the “Best For” strategy was chosen and used with $n = 100$.

4.2.2 K-Fold Cross Validation

Though model directly trained and validated on a specific split may provide a general indication of a model’s performance. Certain splits may benefit or disadvantage the model and may provide inconsistent results. Certain techniques such as k-Fold Cross Validation (k-FCV) have been devised to address this issue.

Figure 4.2.a Diagram of K-Fold Cross Validation [41]

k-FCV works by partitioning the dataset into k equally sized subsets, the model is then trained and evaluated k times on the non “hold-out” partitions, using a different hold-out partition to

evaluate the model each time (Figure 4.2.a). This approach ensures more consistent and representative results across the entire dataset and not just a specific split [41].

4.2.3 Hyperparameter Optimization (Grid Search)

In Machine Learning, a common method to optimize hyperparameters is to use grid search. Grid search involves looping over a set of pre-defined hyperparameter “grid” and assessing the accuracy for each “grid.” Thus “brute-forcing” all combinations to maximize accuracy or to determine a trend.

For conventional machine learning models with closed form solutions i.e. k-NNs, there is only one solution for each dataset, and hence a consistent result for each set of parameters. However, for Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD), as used with neural networks such as CNNs, there exist a possibly infinite number of solutions per dataset. It was therefore decided, to not evaluate the performance per “grid”, but to evaluate the overall trends in accuracy when certain hyperparameters were adjusted.

4.3 Hardware Deployment

Once the pre-processor and model designs were verified on the development machine (PC), the next step was to deploy the various software components to the hardware stack.

Figure 4.3.a Project Hardware Stack

The hardware stack (Figure 4.3.a) consists of: a Raspberry Pi 3B single-board computer, a Nvidia Jetson Nano single-board computer, a Blue Yeti stereo microphone, various power supplies and a DHCP router to ensure connectivity between the devices.

```
/usr/bin/rsync --progress --archive --recursive --delete --exclude-from=".rsyncignore" ./ fbinsect@192.168.0.100:UQ-REIT484X-Project/  
/usr/bin/rsync --progress --archive --recursive --delete --exclude-from=".rsyncignore" ./ jntwo@192.168.0.101:UQ-REIT484X-Project/
```

Figure 4.3.b Software Deployment Script

The process of deploying the software to the production environment was automated using an RSync bash script (Figure 4.3.b), which replicated the entire directory structure of project on the development machine, to both the Jetson and Raspberry Pi.

4.4 Backend Stack

4.4.1 Configuration File

The configuration file “config.json” (Figure 4.4.a) includes all the parameters related to the project, including those for: path, recorder, preprocessor, dataset, train, offload, pipeline, rpi and jetson.

```
{
  "path": {
    "dataset": "./dataset/",
    "states": "./model/",
    "recording": "./recording/"
  },
  "recorder": {
    "length": 4,
    "size_chunk": 1024,
    "channels": 2,
    "signal_sr": 16000
  },
  "preprocessor": {
    "length_segment": 1
  },
}
```

Figure 4.4.a Config File Sample

The parameters must be changed if in Jetson Mode and the network conditions have been changed, i.e. changed DHCP server leading to a different IP address.

4.4.2 Real-Time Classification Pipeline

In order meet the project’s objective of operating autonomously and in real time, a pipeline protocol was developed.

Figure 4.4.b Pipeline (Standalone)

Figure 4.4.c Pipeline (Jetson)

The classification pipeline allows for operation in 2 modes, standalone and Jetson. In standalone mode (Figure 4.4.b), only a single Raspberry Pi is necessary to perform pre-processing and prediction. In Jetson mode (Figure 4.4.c), the pre-processing step is offloaded to the Jetson Nano, with the MFCC/LFCC images being sent back to the Raspberry Pi for the remaining tasks.

Prediction was not performed on the Jetson since PyTorch had limited support and setup was not straightforward, furthermore, the model being used is lightweight and did not cause too much overhead. The pre-processor almost needed as much CPU time as the predictor, therefore the prediction was offloaded to the Jetson.

4.4.3 Web Stack

To accommodate the API endpoints necessary to meet the interoperability objective of this project and for allowing the frontend to display data in real-time, a web stack was used. The web stack consists of the following software tools:

- NGINX, a reverse proxy to serve the API endpoint as well as the frontend.
- MySQL, a database to store insect activity probability datapoints.
- Node Process Manager, to host the frontend.
- Flask, the API server on both the Raspberry Pi and Jetson.

4.4.4 Data API

The Data API – implemented using the Python Flask library, was the key component of this project. It allows the insect classification subsystem to be integrated into a greater ecosystem, i.e. the FarmBot and frontend. The API includes endpoints to return entries (based on time), delete entries, count entries and insert new entries and allows for interoperability with other Integrated Pest Management assets.

The following table lists all the Data API entries available to third parties and internally:

Raspberry Pi API Endpoints		
Endpoint	Description	Sample Response
/api/all	Returns all entries currently in DB in JSON format.	<pre>{ "class": 2, "probability": 0.0, "timestamp": "Thu, 19 Oct 2023 14:25:26 GMT" }, { "class": 1, "probability": 0.0, "timestamp": "Thu, 19 Oct 2023 14:25:26 GMT" }, { "class": 0, "probability": 1.0, "timestamp": "Thu, 19 Oct 2023 14:25:26 GMT" }, }</pre>
/api/last/<n>	Returns the n last entries currently in DB in JSON format.	As above
/api/timelast/<last>	Returns entries recorded in the last [“5m”, “15m”, “1h”]. <last> is a string.	As above
/api/prune/<n>	Removes all entries in the DB older than the latest n.	
/api/count/events	Returns the number of entries currently in DB.	<pre>[{ "COUNT(DISTINCT timestamp)": 344 }]</pre>
/api/count/datapoints	Returns total number of datapoints currently in DB. Should be $entries \times n_{class}$	<pre>[{ "COUNT(*)": 1026 }]</pre>
/api/count/probability	Cumulative probabilities of all entries for each class.	<pre>{ "0": 291.6666759999999, "1": 18.333332, "2": 31.99999199999999 }</pre>

/api/add	Adds a probability entry tuple into the DB.	
/api/pipeline/start	Starts the real-time pipeline.	Pipeline started...
/api/pipeline/stop	Stops the real-time pipeline.	Pipeline stopped...
/api/pipeline/delay/<n>	Sets the delay between each pipeline cycle to n seconds.	Pipeline delay set to 10 seconds...

```
{'0-control': 0.6666666666666666, '1-cricket': 0.0, '2-fly': 0.3333333333333333}
127.0.0.1 -- [18/Oct/2023 22:50:52] "POST /api/add HTTP/1.0" 201 -
Probabilities inserted successfully
```

Figure 4.4.d Example /api/add Insertion

4.5 Frontend Design

To fulfill the project's objective of creating a somewhat intuitive user interface, through which the end user may monitor insect activity in real time, a frontend was created. The frontend was built in ReactJS using the open-source MatX theme as a template and was adapted to include the basic features for managing and viewing insect activity and can be accessed via a web browser using a PC, Tablet or Smartphone (Figure 4.5.a).

Figure 4.5.a Cross-Platform Frontend

The Dashboard page (Figure 4.5.b) features:

- Pipeline Controls: Allowing the classification pipeline to be toggled on/off.
- Event/Datapoint Counts
- Insect Activity Graph: Allowing the user to view insect activity in the last 5, 15 or 60 minutes.
- Total Insect Activity: Allowing the user to view total insect activity (probabilities) stored in the database.

Figure 4.5.b Frontend Dashboard

In addition to the modified Dashboard, dummy pages including Training, Dataset and Settings were created to accommodate future extensions of the project, allowing the model to be re-trainable from within the frontend itself (Figure 4.5.c).

Figure 4.5.c Frontend Menu

4.6 Summary

Figure 4.6.a High-Level Project Overview

(Figure 4.6.a) represents a high-level block diagram of the entire project, illustrating the relationships between the Raspberry Pi and Jetson Nano single-board computers (SBCs), as well as the peripherals including training machines. It also depicts the interaction pathways for end users through the frontend and the integration with the Farmbot system. The FarmBot is represented as a black box, capable of interoperating with this project via the data API.

5 Results

5.1 Classification Model

To perform grid search, initial model hyperparameters need to be determined such that the nearby hyperparameter values may be explored. For this project, 10 and 47 feature maps (convolution channels) were used as the initial “center” value for grid search. The fully connected layer had parameter size of 256. All test cases involved the use of k-FCV with $k = 5$.

Figure 5.1.a Accuracy vs Conv1 Channels

The grid search for the first convolutional layer involved searching 2 channels [8, 12] above and below the center value of 10 (Figure 5.1.a). A negative correlation was found between the number of channels in this layer and the accuracy of the model. However, since there was a higher variance in the results for 8 channels compared to 10 or 12, the number of channels was kept as 10 for the final model.

Figure 5.1.b Accuracy vs Conv2 Channels

The grid search for the second convolutional layer involved searching 5 channels [36, 40, 44, 52, 50] and revealed a positive correlation between the number of channels and model performance (Figure 5.1.b). It was decided that the layer size was to be set 60.

Figure 5.1.c Accuracy vs FC1 Features

The grid search for the fully-connected layer involved searching initially 2 channels [128, 512] revealing a positive correlation between the number of channels and model performance (Figure 5.1.c). After extending the test domain, it was decided that the layer size was to be set to 1024.

Figure 5.1.d Final Model Training Convergence

The final model, used in the demo and report, achieved a moving average accuracy of 93.07 over the final 20 epochs and converged in 110 epochs (Figure 5.1.d). In actuality, the model converged in 10 epochs, however for the loop to stop, the maximum accuracy achieved must remain the best for the next 100 epochs.

It was assumed that mild overfitting would not have great negative impacts on the model since the data variety was very small and the model was being trained on a very homogenous dataset. This assumption was validated by the fact that the model generalized well to unseen sounds in field tests.

5.2 Real-Time Classification Pipeline

After the system was implemented, performance improvements were observed on the master node (Raspberry Pi), by as much as -21.8% , as shown in the table below:

Configuration	Peak CPU Usage (RPI)	Peak CPU Usage (Jetson)
Standalone Mode	37.6%	0%
Jetson Mode	15.8%	39.3%
$\Delta Load$ %	-21.8%	$+39.3\%$

This decreased load on the Raspberry Pi will allow additional processes to run if necessary, including more concurrent database accesses, allowing for a more stable API and frontend in times of high demand. However, there is an asymmetric load increase on the Jetson's CPU, by as much as 39.3% .

Evidently, using Jetson mode over standalone would decrease the overall efficiency of all systems. This is an important tradeoff to consider if the system were to be deployed in an energy-constrained environment as a single Raspberry Pi will usually suffice due to the low model complexity required for prediction.

Figure 5.2.a RPI CPU Usage %

As can be seen in (Figure 5.2.a), the CPU usage on the Raspberry Pi peaks slightly every 10 seconds, corresponding to a record, prediction and database insertion cycle.

5.3 Frontend

In the frontend, all the buttons are successfully configured to control the classification pipeline.

Figure 5.3.a Pipeline Control Function

When the “Start” button is pressed (Figure 5.3.a), an API request is sent to the Flask API server and probabilities begin to be displayed (Figure 5.3.b) and inserted into the database.

```
127.0.0.1 - - [04/Nov/2023 21:04:37] "GET /api/pipeline/start HTTP/1.0" 200 -  
Device Selected = [cpu]  
127.0.0.1 - - [04/Nov/2023 21:04:45] "POST /api/rpi/receive HTTP/1.0" 200 -  
127.0.0.1 - - [04/Nov/2023 21:04:45] "POST /api/rpi/receive HTTP/1.0" 200 -  
127.0.0.1 - - [04/Nov/2023 21:04:45] "POST /api/rpi/receive HTTP/1.0" 200 -  
{'0-control': 1.0, '1-cricket': 0.0, '2-fly': 0.0}
```

Figure 5.3.b Pipeline Control API Response

An example test-case was constructed to evaluate the functionality of the classification pipeline in conjunction with the frontend:

- After a period of random unrelated sounds introduce (to the microphone) unseen cricket sounds.
- Allow cricket sounds to play for 60 seconds then immediately switch to unseen fly sounds.
- Allow fly sounds to play for 60 seconds then immediately switch back to silence (control).

The results reflect the expected behavior of the system, as the cricket probability (green) peaked for approximately 1 minute while cricket sounds were introduced, and this immediately switched to flies (blue) after fly sounds were introduced (Figure 5.3.c). The output returned to control (yellow) after silence was re-introduced.

Figure 5.3.c Classification Test Case

Finally, the aggregate insect activity section of the page – when refreshed – updated successfully, and displayed area under each of the respective shaded areas corresponding to each insect in the table (Figure 5.3.d).

Total Insect Activity	
Class	Total Activity
Control (None)	405.33
Cricket	25.67
Fly	35.00

Figure 5.3.d Aggregate Insect Activity

6 Conclusion

The project achieved all the set objectives in the aim and led to the creation of a fully functional subsystem capable of classifying, quantifying insects based on acoustic recordings, and make this data available via an API and frontend, allowing for easy interoperability and integration into existing FarmBot systems.

In the process of development, a pipeline was developed to classify insect sounds using a convolutional neural network, leveraging extensive audio datasets and whilst maintaining an approach generalizable to n future insect classes. The automated preprocessing pipeline efficiently transformed audio signals into MFCC/LFCC features, addressing class imbalance via undersampling. The CNN architecture was designed systematically, validated by K-Fold Cross-Validation and was optimized through grid search. The deployment on both Raspberry Pi 3B and Nvidia Jetson Nano, complemented by a web stack for real-time classification and an API for system interoperability, allowing end-users as well as third parties to access data stored onboard.

However, the model accuracy attained was not as high as some others in the literature, which utilized similar models. It was hypothesized that the unremarkable model accuracy (93.07%) was due to limitations in the dataset as opposed to the model design, which was shown to result in higher accuracies in the literature. One potential way to address this limitation may be to improve the dataset with a more diverse range of audio samples, as well as the usage of data augmentation techniques outlined in the literature.

In conclusion, this project stands as a testament to the potential for advanced AI technologies to contribute meaningfully to sustainable agriculture and to the broader field of precision agriculture with intelligent, adaptable, and sustainable solutions. The functionalities embedded within the system, from its classification abilities to its integration with third-party ecosystems, pave the way for smarter, data-driven decisions in integrated pest management.

6.1 Future Directions

A few considerations were made as to how the project may be further improved upon in the future:

Multi-node System

This can be achieved by implementing more microphones and Raspberry Pis and storing the base station ID for each event in the master database. This system can also be used to triangulate the position of insects in each area, allowing for more comprehensive IPM solution.

WAN Access to API/Frontend

The frontend may be offloaded to a cloud provider, or the Raspberry Pi(s) may be port-forwarded to allow WAN access. Currently, the system is only capable of being accessed over LAN, and remote administration is impossible.

Dataset, Training and Settings in the Frontend

Due to time constraints, this feature was outside the scope of the project. In the future, the frontend may be updated to allow for editing the dataset and re-training the model, allowing end users to more easily add more insects and improve the model.

Making Model Robust to Background Sounds

The model may be made more robust to background sounds by either: 1) implementing a noise filtering step in the preprocessor or, 2) increasing the control dataset size with recordings of various background sounds not of interest.

7 Figures

Figure 2.1.a Multi-Layer Perceptron Network [13].....	12
Figure 2.1.b Convolutional Neural Network Diagram [15].....	12
Figure 2.2.a Spectrogram [17]	14
Figure 2.2.b Mel Spectrogram [18].....	15
Figure 2.2.c Mel Filter Banks [16].....	16
Figure 2.3.a FarmBot Genesis Garden Mechanism [22]	18
Figure 2.3.b Farmaudio I/O Overview [22].....	19
Figure 2.3.c Jetson Nano FPS Performance w.r.t DL Network [23]	20
Figure 2.4.d Jetson Nano Overview [1]	20
Figure 4.1.a Librosa Pre-processor Block Diagram.....	28
Figure 4.1.b TorchAudio Preprocessor Diagram [38]	29
Figure 4.1.c Sample [MFCC, LFCC] Feature Image for Cricket	30
Figure 4.1.d Dataset Folder Structure	30
Figure 4.1.e Undersampling and Oversampling [39].....	31
Figure 4.1.f Dataset Size Before/After Resampling	32
Figure 4.2.a Diagram of K-Fold Cross Validation [41].....	33
Figure 4.3.a Project Hardware Stack	35
Figure 4.3.b Software Deployment Script	35
Figure 4.4.a Config File Sample	36
Figure 4.4.b Pipeline (Standalone).....	37
Figure 4.4.c Pipeline (Jetson).....	37
Figure 4.4.d Example /api/add Insertion.....	39
Figure 4.5.a Cross-Platform Frontend	40
Figure 4.5.b Frontend Dashboard	41
Figure 4.5.c Frontend Menu.....	42
Figure 4.6.a High-Level Project Overview	43
Figure 5.1.a Accuracy vs Conv1 Channels.....	44
Figure 5.1.b Accuracy vs Conv2 Channels.....	45
Figure 5.1.c Accuracy vs FC1 Features	45
Figure 5.1.d Final Model Training Convergence.....	46

Figure 5.2.a RPI CPU Usage %	47
Figure 5.3.a Pipeline Control Function	48
Figure 5.3.b Pipeline Control API Response	48
Figure 5.3.c Classification Test Case.....	49
Figure 5.3.d Aggregate Insect Activity	49

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9 Appendices

9.1 Appendix A: Grid Search Results

conv1_chann	conv2_chann	fc1_features	accuracy_kfc
8	36	128	90.146
8	36	256	92.413
8	36	512	92.253
8	40	128	91.126
8	40	256	91.113
8	40	512	91.613
8	44	128	91.773
8	44	256	91.7795
8	44	512	92.826
8	44	1024	92.89
8	48	128	90.96
8	48	256	91.133
8	48	512	91.486
8	52	128	90.5
8	52	256	92.733
8	52	512	91.538
8	52	1024	92.413
8	60	256	92.573
8	60	512	91.538
8	60	1024	93.213
10	36	128	92.406
10	36	256	91.286
10	36	512	91.613
10	40	128	90.46
10	40	256	92.886
10	40	512	92.253
10	44	128	90.78
10	44	256	91.613
10	44	512	91.766
10	48	128	90.493
10	48	256	92.573
10	48	512	91.613
10	52	128	91.773
10	52	256	91.12
10	52	512	92.273
12	36	128	90.96
12	36	256	91.293
12	36	512	91.793
12	40	128	90.653
12	40	256	91.28
12	40	512	91.113
12	44	128	91.793
12	44	256	91.286
12	44	512	92.253
12	48	128	90.459
12	48	256	90.66
12	48	512	92.393
12	52	128	90.153
12	52	256	91.919
12	52	512	91.293